

TOPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF *DESCHAMPSIA ANTARCTICA* POPULATIONS ROBUSTNESS BASED ON A MONITORING STUDY ON GALINDEZ ISLAND

N. Miryuta¹, V. Ivanets ¹, I. Parnikoza^{1,2}

¹State Institution National Antarctic Scientific Center, Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine;

²Institute of Molecular Biology and Genetics, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine; i.yu.parnikoza@imbg.org.ua

This study aims to analyze the robustness of *Deschampsia antarctica* populations in different micro-growth conditions. Since the study was conducted on objects belonging to an open ecological system, the topological analysis of their robustness and changes in robustness over time was carried out by determining the eigenvalues for the intervals 2013/14 – 2020/21 and 2013/14 – 2020/24 seasons.

Monitoring was carried out on eleven experimental *D. antarctica* plant populations sampled from Galindez Island (Argentine Islands, the maritime Antarctic) during the 2013/14 – 2020/24 seasons. The three most variable morphometric characteristics were used for the topological analysis: population size $x(t)$, average values of leaf length $y(t)$ and flower length $z(t)$ in the dynamics of 8 and 11 seasons. We selected exponential curves by the CurveExpert1.3 program for the sets $x(t)=\exp_{\lambda_1 t}$, $y(t) =\exp_{\lambda_2 t}$, $z(t) =\exp_{\lambda_3 t}$ and determined the fit reliability. The attractor type was determined by the eigenvalues set according to the classification given by Eigen.

The case when λ are real or complex conjugate numbers was considered. In eigenvalues terms attractors types for three indices for 2013/14 – 2020/21 seasons were:

The robust focus when all $\lambda < 0$ is the attractor. When $\text{Re } \lambda \rightarrow 0$ roots approach the imaginary axis. As a result, the initial robust focus turns into a limit cycle, because periodic oscillations in time arise in the system. As a result of these fluctuations the system transited into the limit cycle when all $\text{Re } \lambda = 0$.

The limit cycle when all $\text{Re } \lambda = 0$ or all $\lambda < 0$ is the attractor (special point) of the system in which undamped oscillations occur. This attractor belongs to non-coarse systems which trajectories undergo significant changes with small variations (fluctuations) of parameters. Four populations (D1, D3, D9, D11) were in limit cycle state.

The robust torus is an attractor under the conditions when two value $\lambda = 0$, one value $\lambda < 0$. Four populations (D2, D5, D6, D7) were in a robust torus state.

The chaotic (strange) attractor is formed under the conditions $\lambda_1 > 0$, $\lambda_2 = 0$, $\lambda_3 < 0$, has at least two special points, and the adjacent trajectories diverge under slight changes in the initial conditions. One population (D4) was in the strange attractor state.

Unrobust torus is a phase portrait of the system, when $\lambda_1 = 0$, $\lambda_2 = 0$, $\lambda_3 > 0$, and it is not an attractor. Two populations (D10, D12) were in an unrobust torus state.

Through three seasons, a topological analysis was conducted again for the interval of 2013/14 – 2020/24 seasons. It has been shown that changing external conditions can lead to some populations transitioning from one robust state to another or from an unrobust state to a robust one. In particular, the penguin nesting population invasion over the past 3 years has destroyed one population (D4), whose state was described by a strange attractor over 8 seasons. One population (D6) has transited from the robust torus state to the strange attractor state, and another population (D10) has transited from the unrobust torus state to the limit cycle state in the last three of the 11 research seasons.